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‘European Intelligence’ From the Perspectives of Cognitive Psychology-Neurobiology: Why are the Europeans what they are Today?

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Abstract

Black women and Black men gave birth to white children who suppose to be brothers to Black children. But over thousands of years in isolation, white people developed fictitious theories to make themselves look different and distinct. The Neanderthals they tend to associate themselves with through sexual contact left no civilization, so it is difficult to judge the outcome of this sexual relationship. While the paintings in the caves in modern France look suspicious, Black people, on the other hand, built civilizations all over the planet: Ancient Egyptians, Nubians, the Incas, Ancient Rome, Mesopotamia, Indian Dravidians, etc. Evidence from history through the Roman Empire shows that White people were human beings like all others and, therefore, they did not treat them differently. The investigation used cognitive psychology and neurobiology perspectives to explain the successful experiences of Germanic tribes and the Slavs in Central Asia. The theoretical investigation uses existing data and argues that they are not distinct though there had been a mixture of genes with some tribes in Central Asia. Europeans' use of their local languages and the employment of scientific theories and methods of inquiry have something to do with their intelligence and overall success in the world. The relegation of the religion's authority and the replacement with reason and science methods has enabled Europeans to become successful with cognitive intelligence. Intelligence has something to do with knowledge acquisition with the blood language and sciences in imbibing knowledge. Where human beings use their local languages and the addition of the methods of scientific inquiry, there will be marginal differences in intelligence acquisition. The discoveries the researchers Paul Broca and Carl Wernicke made with neurobiology show that language speaking is a complex human phenomenon that human beings should take seriously in daily discourses. No wonder it gave the Europeans unique problems when they had to depend on Latin to imbibe knowledge and use it to carry out responsibilities. Intelligence has something to do with the blood language, local language, or culturally provided language in imbibing knowledge in the physical world. Scientific theories and appropriate scientific methods should be driven by the use of Mathematics and logic. Emerging technological societies, such as China, Malaysia, Singapore, etc., testify to these modern methods of reaching progress in education.

Keywords: Barbarian Archetype, Broca's Area, Cognitive Psychology, Collective Unconscious, Europeans, Genetic, Handicap, Injuries, Neurobiology, Neurological Disorders, Psychedelic Drugs, War Neanderthals, Wernicke Area

1. Preamble

Recent studies have established that the Europeans (commonly known as *Homo sapiens*, which means ‘wisdom’ or ‘uses thinking to solve problems’) originated and migrated from Africa and certain parts of India to stay in the

Asian prairies for several thousands of years (around 40 000)[1]. During their nomadic lives, Europeans accumulated enormous experiences that had something to do with their success in the present world. We can explain some important events of these experiences from Cognitive Psychology and Neurobiology perspectives.

The genetic hypothesis that they mated with Neanderthals, an ancient archaic species in the primordial period, and, as a result, acquired their favorable genes have not been disputed. But even these experiential contacts that resulted consequently in sexual intercourse could not explain their success and adaptation in the world because the Neanderthals, as archaic species, left no civilizations that could aid us in deciding the positive outcome of the experience of the contact[2]. Earlier, some renowned authors noted that the Europeans had not shown any 'superior intelligence' when they emerged from their thousands of years in isolation in central Asia. Because they could scarcely read or write when they encountered the Romans, their masters, who had built superb civilization in Europe. This was later to help tame them from their brute behaviors and cultural practices, which they had acquired from encountering the Nomadic tribes of Central Asia and Europe.

In this paper, we shall set forth the different hypotheses which will help us explain why the Europeans, specifically the Germanic tribes and the Slavs, who were known as the barbarians, have achieved remarkable success in the present world. These explanations will encourage us to assert that though they had encountered different nomadic tribes such as the Huns, the Ancient Romans, and other less well-known tribes as they moved back to Europe (formerly North Africa), none of these aided them to adapt more than the scientific-blood language hypothesis, which opened doors and other avenues such as imbibing and "stealing" of ideas and technologies from the East and West that comprise the modern world. The Religious Reformation in Germany that later spread across Europe and the scientific revolutions capacitated modern Europeans during the last 600 years ago to make strides and invest in efficient scientific institutions and innovative banking systems, which have yielded stupendous outcomes for these adventurous human beings.

2. A Neurobiology Theory: The Handicap Theory

Despite their insistence on having mated with the archaic tribes, such as the Neanderthals, the Europeans were primitive and engaged in all manner of evil practices that were practiced in Africa and other cultures around the globe. In this context, they could not have regarded themselves as more civilized than all others. They were in gutters like all other human beings that sacrificed humans to their petty gods and depended on the same gods for their survival against misfortunes. But it seems they had one disadvantage that later turned out to become an advantage in disguise. This had been inherent in them due to their genetic makeup, which we consider to be statistical rather than deterministic law. Genetically, they lacked melanin. This is a broad term for a group of natural pigments found in most organisms. Melanin pigments are produced in a specialized group of cells known as melanocytes.

There are five basic types of melanin: eumelanin, pheomelanin, neuromelanin, all melanin, and pheomelanin. The most common type is eumelanin, of which there are two types— brown eumelanin and black eumelanin. Eumelanin is produced through a multistage chemical process known as melanogenesis, where the oxidation of the amino acid tyrosine is followed by polymerization. Pheomelanin, which is produced when melanocytes are malfunctioning due to the derivation of the gene to its recessive format is a cysteine-derivative that contains polybenzothiazine portions that are largely responsible for the red or yellow tint given to some skin or hair colors. Neuromelanin is found in the brain. Research has been undertaken to investigate its efficacy in treating neurodegenerative disorders such as Parkinson's [3].

Europeans lacked black melanin which meant that they were not naturally strong as all others that had the black pigment in them. Their bone is understood to be about roughly 20% weaker than the normal African or those other human beings that possess the black pigment. We are tempted to hypothesize that due to this lack, their strength had to be compensated with the good use of their brains in thinking and making small decisions that need the use of strength. Here, we could take a case from the female organ called 'the Clitoris' as an example.'

The Clitoris hypothesis states that when this organ which has the most important role as a sensitive organ that gives the woman apex sexual stimulation and satisfaction is cut or severed by doctors through circumcision, the sexual sensitiveness does not go away. The sensitive feelings escape to other parts of the female body, such as within her thighs, around her labia, around her neck, or deep inside the vagina. Thus, though this woman could no longer experience her g-point at the severed clitoris, compensation is gained, which does not make her lose the sexual stimulation and the enjoyment she receives as a functioning woman [4].

The bigger brain hypothesis is attached to the handicapped hypothesis. Here, it is surmised that due to the migration experiences, the Europeans ingeniously had access to good food in the form of assortments of vegetables that were nutritious and abundant meat, which furnished them with proteins and other essential mineral sources for their development of intelligence. Dairy products helped them to obtain milk and cheese, which yielded them bone strength because of the calcium contents they gained regularly. Scientists have confirmed the bigger brain hypothesis many years ago as authentic which is estimated to be the right source of European intelligence rather than any form of mutation that occurred in their genes. But still, others disagree with it. Recently, the Chinese and Japanese heads have undermined this theory, so now they speak of white or grey matter. Einstein and a few other geniuses had more of these substances than the average head [5, 6].

Same As the All Others Hypothesis. This is additional research that has shown that *the genetic makeup of all human beings is the same. It was conducted by international researchers and later reported publicly in the White House, Washington DC, AD 2000 found this important information. That "all human beings are 99.99% the same at the DNA level and the remaining 0.1% genetic variations that exist seldom segregate in a manner that conforms to the racial boundaries constructed by social political means" (White House, June 2000) [7, 8].*

It, therefore, does not seem complicated to employ the *Clitoris hypothesis* in the context of the handicapped theory as some studies among ordinary handicapped in general have shown to provide them minor advantages in making careful decisions about anything they accomplish as they are always conscious of this disadvantage when they have to embark on carrying out any function that pertains to their survival or existence.

3. Cognition and the Nomadic Tribe Hypothesis

Europeans in Central Asia found themselves among diverse tribes whose way of life was primitive and barbaric. These Asian tribes were Mongols, Kazaks, Uzbekistanis, Afghans, Pakistanis, Tajiks, Chechenia, Kyrgyzstan, and some minor Chinese tribes. They received immense distractions because of the confusion they experienced in the environments. These hindrances did not help the Europeans to develop any proper civilization when they sojourned among these barbaric nomadic tribes in the central part of Asia. Except for the Chinese tribes that were more civilized, these nomadic tribes were cruel and primitive, and constantly used barbaric wars, domination, and kidnapping to distract them from either learning writing or developing civilized culture. The lifestyles of these diverse tribes were extreme barbarism and toughness, which the Europeans had to endure constantly in this hectic milieu.

Presently, the dominant behavioral characteristics of the Russian tribes allow us to visualize what happened in those periods as we witness the modern wars between the Russians and its neighboring tribes/countries, such as Ukrainians, Georgians, and Chechenia people. History has recorded a clear picture of what it looked like in Central Asia. Several tribes knew no civilized way of living; they had to move from one place to another with their cattle herds, and while not planting for food, they performed other chores that prevented other people to live and to develop a stable cultural life. In short, Central Asia saw later the emergence of the Huns, Mongols, Kazaks, etc., who exhibited cruel manners with dealing with their kidnaped tribes, toughness and barbarism, lacking civilization and civic manners, brute, etc. These different groups of people that one can describe as living in hordes gave no peace and tranquility minds to the Europeans. So, in the end, the latter imbibed their way of life, which did not help them as a people [9].

This manner helped them to acquire cognition, that is, mental action or process of acquiring knowledge and understanding through thought, experience, and the senses. But this form of cognition was primitive like all other groups of people because it was not advanced and it was without science and its special method of inquiry.

4. Transformation Period: The Roman Empire Hypothesis

The Germanic Tribes and some Slavs' migration to Europe (formerly North Africa) have been described to be the result of wars between some of these dominant tribes in Central Asia. In particular, the names of the Mongols and Attila the Hun had been mentioned. Their appearance in Europe brought with them these same tribes who were out there to fight for booty and material things. They continued to exhibit cruelty, barbarity, toughness, and domination characters. Some authors have described their appearance in Europe as extreme hunger due to famine. Because of their nomadic life, they hardly planted and cultivated crops and vegetables of different sorts, so it was not our place that they were looking for a place to plunder and satisfy their thirst and hunger because of the prolonged famine that occurred in Central Asia due to drought.

Meanwhile, in Europe and North Africa, the Mediterranean Regions right unto Spain and the Atlantic Coast, the Romans, the Civilized Masters of Europe, had conquered many tribes and subjugated them into vassal states. The emergence of the Germanic Tribes and the Slavs brought an influx into the Empire and commenced to cause chaos to this well-developed civilization. The Romans began to fight these different tribes whom they called "Barbarians" due to their uncultured manners and the cruel manners they dealt with their captors as they waged their copious wars. The Europeans mimicked the same manners Central Asian Tribes did to their captors or slaves, so the Romans could not see any way of amalgamating them into their Empire. They regarded them as outsiders and did not allow them to enter these orderly-mannered societies in the civilized Roman Empire.

Notable Roman authors and generals have described the entrance of these Germanic tribes and some Slavs into the Roman Empire. Centuries passed after another while successive conquests of the tribes occurred in Europe. These tribes were named as follows. The western German tribes consisted of the Marcomanni, Alamanni, Franks, Angles, and Saxons; while the Eastern tribes that inhabited the north of the Danube consisted of the Vandals, Gepids, Ostrogoths, and Visigoths. The Alans, Burgundians, and Lombards are less easy to be identified. As a linguistic group, modern Germanic peoples include the Afrikaners, Austrians, Danes, Dutch, English, Flemish, Frisians, Germans, Icelanders, Lowland Scots, Norwegians, Swedes, and others (including diaspora populations, such as some groups of European Americans). The Vikings are also a Germanic tribe. The Vikings were one of many different Germanic peoples. There are three major branches of Germanic languages: East Germanic, West Germanic, and North Germanic. The most violent Germanic tribe was the Chatti. It was the Germanic tribe that became one of the most powerful opponents of the Romans during the 1st century AD of the Roman Empire. During that period the Chatti expanded from their homeland near the upper Visurgis (Weser) River, across the Taunus highlands in the Moenus (Main) River valley, defeating the Cherusci and other neighboring tribes [10].

But during Emperor-Philosopher, Marcus Aurelius, who is known as the most educated and polished emperor Rome ever had, the Germanic tribes were finally accepted officially into the society of *the civilized Roman people*, and so they had the opportunity to learn the Roman Civic Education, Roman Laws, and Institutions, Roman Mannerism, Taming to desist from being barbaric and cruel, Settling down, they learned strategic War techniques and Weapon Building, positive Behavioral Characteristics, and unique amalgamation.

The **Pax Romana** (Latin for 'Roman peace') is a roughly 200-year-long timespan of Roman history which is identified as a period and as a golden age of increased as well as sustained Roman imperialism, relative peace and order, prosperous stability, hegemonial power, and regional expansion, despite several revolts and wars, and continuing competition with Parthia. It dates traditionally as commencing with the accession of Augustus, founder of the Roman principate, in 27 BC and concluding in 180 AD with the death of Marcus Aurelius, the last of the "Five Good Emperors." [11]

The most important legacy of the Roman civilization is still felt today in Western culture in areas such as government, law, language, architecture, engineering, and religion. Many modern-day governments are modeled

after the Roman Republic. Others talk of the five legacies of the Roman Empire and the Roman civilization as were made in art and architecture, technology and science, medicine, literature, language, religion, and law.

5. Science and Blood Language Hypothesis

5.1. Languages and Reading

Europeans became assimilated into the emerging cultures of Europe, but as a rule, the Latin language was used in academic circles and other major centers of learning. The Christian Church, which had power in these learning centers required that this Latin language was the one they used in imbibing knowledge and carrying out responsibilities. So, in the Ecclesiastical Church and the Universities, only a few people could read, write, and comprehend. This condition resulted in major problems concerning illiteracy and indescribable ignorance in the European centers of culture. A change from the Latin language to their various languages as tools or instruments in imbibing knowledge helped the European citizens to spearhead the Enlightenment that banished ignorance and illiteracy from among the mass population.

In *The Establishment of the Select Society for Promoting the Reading and Speaking of the English Language in Scotland, 1761* an Extract from a periodical (NLS shelfmark: Sc. Mag, July 1761), [12] we find important information on the British use of the native language. The Select Society, an Edinburgh debating society, was founded in 1754 by the painter Allan Ramsay. Its stated aims were the 'pursuit of philosophical inquiry and the improvement of members in the art of speaking.' The membership included many of the outstanding figures of the Scottish Enlightenment, among them Adam Smith, David Hume, and Hugh Blair. These giants Enlightenment scholars promoted the 'English tongue' in reading, writing, and making philosophical inquiries. 'Following a course of lectures on spoken English, given in Edinburgh by the Irish actor Thomas Sheridan in June 1761, there was an increased enthusiasm for studying and promoting the 'English tongue.' In July 1761, 'Scots Magazine' reported that the plan of creating a new establishment' for this purpose was to be put before the committee of the Select Society [13].

5.2. Religious Reformation

The Reformation was the work of religious scholars that were against the manner of teachings in the Church and the vice of corruption that was taking place in the Roman Catholic Church. Those Biblical scholars, such as Dr. Martin Luther, a German Cleric, opposed the Church leadership by nailing down his 95 theses that challenged the abuses in the Holy Roman Church [14]. The results were the great schism that led to the divisions in the World Wide Church of God. Those who followed these scholars and demanded separate denominations were known as the Protestants. In England, John Wesley and his brother translated the Bible into English for their Methodist denomination. The importance of the Reformation was that it led to the priesthood of all church members, and it later pushed ahead freedom of worship and the ability to read the Bible in one's language. The protestant ethic was capable of making individuals hard working and initiating missionary work into the world that spread Enlightenment to the people of other continents of the world. *The Protestant Ethic and the Spirit of Capitalism* (German: *Die protestantische Ethik und der Geist des Kapitalismus*), which was authored by Max Weber, a German sociologist, economist, and politician, informed us about the magic of this ideology[15]. They were a series of essays, which the original German text was composed in 1904 and 1905 and was translated into English for the first time by American sociologist Talcott Parsons in 1930. It is considered a founding text in economic sociology and a milestone contribution to sociological thought.

Weber's scholarly discussion on capitalism in Northern Europe began when the Protestant (particularly Calvinist) ethic influenced large numbers of people to work in the secular world, developing their enterprises and engaging in trade and wealth accumulation for investment. The Protestant work ethic was the energy behind the unplanned and uncoordinated emergence of social forms of capitalism in modern Europe. Apart from Calvinists, Weber also debated (especially Pietisms) Methodists, Baptists, Quakers, and Moravians (specifically, referring to the Herrnhut-based community under Count von Zinzendorf's spiritual lead).

5.3. *Scientific Revolution and the Age of Enlightenment*

The Age of Enlightenment concomitantly coincided with the scientific revolution; here, knowledge from the Ancient Roman philosophers and Arabic scholars helped European academics to make inventions. These were the works of other civilizations, which they copied and built upon their work. They were not originators of them.

The Scientific Revolution commenced a drastic change in scientific thought that emerged during the 16th and 17th centuries, especially in Europe. A new comprehension of nature transpired during the Scientific Revolution, substituting the Greek interpretation of the world that had controlled science for almost 2,000 years. The Scientific discipline became an autonomous discipline, apparently distinct from philosophy and technology, and these possessed utilitarian objectives. Science, consequently, superseded Christianity as the principal point of European civilization.

The Scientific Revolution commenced with astronomy. Although there had been earlier theories of the possibility of Earth's motion, the Polish astronomer Nicolaus Copernicus was the first to theorize a comprehensive heliocentric theory. This was equal in scope and predictive power to Ptolemy's geocentric system. Encouraged by the desire to satisfy Plato's dictum, the Polish priest's theory overthrew traditional astronomy because of its alleged violation of the principle of uniform circular motion and its lack of unity and harmony as a system of the world. Utilizing the same data as Ptolemy, Copernicus turned the world inside out, putting the Sun at the center and setting Earth into motion around it. The Astronomer Priest's theory, published in 1543, retained a qualitative straightforwardness that Ptolemaic astronomy appeared not to have fulfilled.

It appears the scientific revolution laid the foundations for the Age of Enlightenment, which centered on *reason as the principal foundation of authority and legitimacy* and emphasized the importance of the scientific method. This took place in the 18th century when the Enlightenment thrived. Here, scientific authority commenced to dislodge the authority of religion, and its related disciplines until then seen as legitimately scientific (e.g., alchemy and astrology). Religious authority lost scientific credibility.

Science came to play a leading role in Enlightenment discourse and thought. Many Enlightenment philosophers, writers, and thinkers had backgrounds in the sciences, and associated scientific advancement with the overthrow of religion and traditional authority in favor of the development of free speech and thought [16].

5.4. *Scientific Institutions*

As the scientific revolution became successful, Europeans established scientific institutions which utilized sciences to conduct research seriously. This was not possible before the reformation when science was not considered an authority. Later, there was an emphasis on STEM.

5.4.1. Types of scientific institutions

Scientists received support from at least three institutions: research institutions, funding institutions, and professional societies.

Research institutions physically house scientists and provide research facilities; they include many colleges and universities, government organizations like the US Geological Survey, and corporations like DuPont or Exxon-Mobil.

Professional societies facilitate the communication of the results of scientific research and foster the development of scientific communities, hosting meetings like conferences and workshops. These societies may be specific to a discipline, such as the Society of Vertebrate Paleontology, or broad and all-encompassing, such as the American Association for the Advancement of Science.

Funding institutions, like the National Science Foundation and the National Institutes of Health, provide grant money to scientists through a competitive process so that they can conduct research.

An individual scientist may work at one or more research institutions, belong to several professional societies, and receive funding from multiple sources. These contacts can influence a scientist's research positively. Likewise, the institutions received influences from the communities of scientists that make up their membership [17].

5.5. Investment in Banking and Acquisition of Wealth

By far, what helped the Europeans to seize and dominate the world was their financial acquisition and investment in banking industries. Some powerful writers such as the Scottish philosopher Adam Smith and his book, *The Wealth of Nations*, published in 1776, and John Maynard Keynes, an English economist, and philosopher whose ideas fundamentally changed the theory and practice of macroeconomics and the economic policies of governments. *The Wealth of Nations* was the product of seventeen years of notes and earlier studies, and an observation of conversation among economists of the time [18]. While *The General Theory of Employment, Interest, and Money*, published in late 1936, was the theory and practice of macroeconomics and the economic policies that helped governments [19]. We shall not spend too much time delving into this as any attempt to discuss it in length could easily lead us astray. But, let us leave the banking industry as a whole and briefly discuss investment banking and how through research Europeans gained wealth that solidified their power and wealth. What Is Investment Banking?

Investment banking is a variant of banking that systematizes large, complex financial transactions such as mergers or initial public offering (IPO) underwriting. These are the banks that raise money for companies which include underwriting the issuance of new securities for a corporation, municipality, or other institution. They manage a corporation's Initial Public Offering. These banks also issue advice in mergers, acquisitions, and reorganizations. Investment bankers 'experts usually have the bulk of information on the pulse of the current investment climate. They at the same time support their clients to navigate the complex world of high finance.

5.6. Investment Banking, Power and Fundamentals in Research

Like all other fields of studies, investment banking received tremendous research and innovation which gave the Europeans a greater footing in the financial centers of the world which expanded from London, New York, and Hong Kong. Investment Research helped them in their analyzing the performance of various financial instruments like stocks, mutual funds, bonds, debentures, etc. It also helped to provide an investor with a perspective on how the company is performing. These researchers in investment banks advise companies on acquiring, selling, or merging with other companies and issuing debt and equity. The research analysts assist the bank in proposing these decisions by researching industries and markets, building financial models, and giving investment presentations.

Investment banking offers financial services to companies seeking to raise capital, while equity research professionals analyze publicly traded companies and make investment recommendations. An investment banking analyst prepares pitch books and information memorandums [20].

5.6.1. The IMF

The IMF is one of the two institutions that give permanent power to the Europeans in the world. It determines the sort of development that should be undertaken by the poor developing countries in the world. The IMF promotes global macroeconomic and financial stability and provides policy advice and capacity development support to help countries build and maintain strong economies. The IMF gives short- and medium-term loans to help countries that are going through the balance of payments problems and difficulty meeting international payment obligations. The loans of the IMF are given to struggling nations mainly by quota contributions from its members. The organization has staff who are fundamentally economists with enormous experience in macroeconomic and financial policies [21].

5.6.2. The World Bank

The second of the two most powerful institutions in the world that Europeans control is The World Bank. The bank promotes long-term economic development and poverty reduction by providing technical and financial support to help member countries implement reforms or projects, such as building schools, providing water and electricity, fighting disease, and protecting the environment. Its financial assistance is long-term and is funded by member country contributions through bond issuance. Its staff is also specialists on specific issues, such as education sectors and climate issues [22].

5.6.3. Summary

The IMF and The World Bank are the two most powerful financial organizations that Europeans use to control the world and other interest groups. These enable them to dictate measures to developed as well as developing nations concerning how they perform in the economic and modern market. Some scholars also add the power of the dollar as a currency. The American dollar commands respect and power in the whole world. Investment banking handles principally sourcing funds for governments, companies, and other financial units. Its operations consist of guaranteeing fresh debt and equity securities for all types of businesses and corporations. These banks work to facilitate mergers and acquisitions, reorganizations, and broker trades for institutions as well as private potential investors. The businessmen who work with Investment bank function among governments, corporations, and other groups. These men plan and manage the financial aspects of large projects. In the United States, for example, Investment banks were legally separated from other types of commercial banks from 1933 to 1999 when the Glass-Steagall Act that segregated them was abolished.

6. Conquest—Domination and Manipulative Behavior Hypothesis

Science has shown that it has the power to unravel the mystery that exists in the physical world. It has capacitated human beings to understand the world that surpasses all other disciplines. What makes science the apex source of knowledge is that it does not concern itself with the explanation that pertains to supernatural beings. God does not come into the equation. Objective manner to the study of any object in space becomes the concern of man. Man depends on his brain and other sophisticated instruments to deal with problems and predicaments that confront him.

As the local tongue and science facilitated reading and comprehension, scholars in various scientific fields increased. This concomitantly happened as the division of labor made specialization possible, and scholars could devote themselves to minute objects and problems with care. The philosopher David Hume asserted that in the 1500s the number of people who could read and write was not up to 200000 in the United Kingdom. The local language was one of the main reasons the English came together as a nation to conquer the world.

The introduction of the local tongue thus helped with mass education in the European countries that equipped them with knowledge, power, unity, and patriotism. Due to incessant wars, research in weapons and arms dealing increased among Europeans. The results led to expansionism, where a nation that felt strong because of the weapon acquisition could walk or enter another's land and confiscate it. These happened among the naive, ignorant, and illiterate tribes in South America, North America, Africa, and Asia Pacific islands. The scramble for Africa was possible because access to weapons made Europeans divide the continent among themselves.

Domination was in the form of slavery, colonies, confiscation, and trade malpractices. These made it possible to confiscate many valuable lands, mineral resources, and favorable habitable parts of the rest of the nations around the world. The bad practices used in Central Asia and later North Africa (Europe) admonished them to continue to utilize it to take whatever they wanted in another part of the world. Moreover, they gained recognition and attention for employing the same things the naive pioneers had described in the religious texts as a legitimate manner of acquiring what one wanted. In the Bible, the strength of a group of people could allow them to use war to claim that land from the owner. During these periods, colonists, businessmen, and missionaries agreed on the same approach to seize and enrich themselves with other groups/tribes' lands [23].

They employed manipulative behavior in the same manner that they managed smoothly to seize the world without the slighted hindrance from the poor and innocent inhabitants. This occurred in South and North America, including its neighboring islands. Africa and India, as well as the Asia Pacific islands' inhabitants, suffered.

This was the period when the scrupulous among them, mostly academicians, took advantage of this leniency among ignorant tribes who happened to be in the same situation as Europeans so many centuries ago and coined the term superiority and super race. Because of illiteracy and extreme ignorance, the citizens accepted these experiences. Since this was a false premise, the deductions following it had to be defended by the so-called scientists; they buttressed manipulation with fictitious developments of theories.

Currently, the repulsion made some honest scholars disbelieve it, though there exists the majority who adhere to this outdated principle through ignorance and literacy. What is more, some centers of learning stick to this manipulative behavior. They use money and influence to develop theories that support and nurture this ideology. Though they are aware that there is no truth in them, they still use all their power and influence to keep the status quo to maintain it.

The Romans took their precious time to study these Germanic tribes and Slavs who lacked physical stamina. They saw the difference between them and black men as resulting from the absence of melanin because black women gave birth to them in the first place. They could hardly perform strenuous work despite their outward appearances that looked admirable. They were quick to comprehend why they could not build any civilization on their own because they occupied themselves with frivolous chores and war as distractions. In Ancient Egypt during the early dynasty, these whites worked as servants. Some early kingdoms used them as serfs. The Roman citizens were mostly mulatto (Mulatto is a racial classification that refers to people of mixed African and European ancestry) and black men that never claimed that any tribe was more human than the other, even though they were aware of the sequence of events that occurred to another tribe to dominate the other [24].

7. Results of the Theoretical Discourse

7.1. Cognitive Psychology: European Aggressive Behavior and Development of Personality

The Clitoris hypothesis, the bigger brain hypothesis, the Nomadic Tribe hypothesis, and the entire Roman Empire hypothesis help in explaining the development of aggressive behavior by the European citizens. One can also explain to a large extent, the development of the personality of the Europeans. I state formally that the factors are numerous and powerful. Notwithstanding other minor conditions may underpin and strengthen the overall vindictive characteristics of the human being known as the "European." So where the Africans and all other human beings may see them as friends, acquaintances, and newcomers, the Europeans only see the foes, enemies, competitors, or adversaries.

These vindictive characteristics enshrine in what Sigmund Freud has called the "unconsciousness" or "collective unconscious" and what Carl Gustav Jung calls "the archetype" of the European mind such that wherever the European finds himself he becomes restless. This may have some additional implication that connotes what I call "existential anxiety." "Existential anxiety is a feeling of dread or panic that arises when a person confronts the limitations of their existence. Thoughts of death, the meaninglessness of life, or the insignificance of self, can all trigger existential anxiety." [25]

The concept of an archetype, from Ancient Greek ἀρχῶ 'to begin,' and τύπος 'sort, type' appears in areas relating to behavior, historical psychology, and literary analysis.

The following can be an archetype:

1. A statement, pattern of behavior, prototype, "first" form, or a main model that other statements, patterns of behavior, and objects copy, emulate, or "merge" into. Informal synonyms frequently used for this

definition include "standard example," "basic example," and the longer-form "archetypal example"; mathematical archetypes often appear as "canonical examples."

2. The Platonic concept of *the pure form* embodies the fundamental characteristics of a thing.
3. A collectively-inherited unconscious idea, a pattern of thought, image, etc. that is universally present, in individual psyches, as in Jungian psychology.
4. A constantly-recurring symbol or motif in literature, painting, or mythology. This definition refers to the recurrence of characters or ideas sharing similar traits throughout various, seemingly unrelated cases in classic storytelling, media, etc. This usage of the term draws from both comparative anthropology and Jungian archetypal theory.

Archetypes are also very close analogies to instincts in that long before any consciousness develops it is the impersonal and inherited traits of human beings that present and motivate human behavior. They also continue to influence feelings and behaviors even after some degree of consciousness develops later.

I refer to the number 1 and 3, which both Freud and Jung use to symbolize what I think is the "main model," "pattern of behavior," "A collectively-inherited unconscious idea," or "a pattern of thought." [26, 27, & 28]

7.2. Social Perception and Cognition in War. European and the War Archetype

The Europeans have the barbarians' war archetype that compares to preparing long in advance even when the shadow of war was nowhere near them. They have restless spirits-- existential anxiety that admonish them to yearn for it. Ordinary smoke could rekindle the war spirit that would interpret the scent of gunpowder. Normal human beings would think about war and weapons, but Barbarians would make their plight to work all the time toward it because war was a hobby in the barbarian world.

The barbarian archetype is unpredictable and always seeking to dominate in power, building infrastructure and utilizing them toward ensuing war in the present and future. Later, I shall discuss the manipulative behavioral characteristics as the false premise of being "superior human beings." The behavior attributed to the barbarian archetype is a hypothesis that needs support not only with reasons but with constant war-making that is regarded as a hobby in the barbarians' world.

7.3. War Stimulate Memories that Offer Compelling Therapy to Aggressive Europeans

While the people are perplexed at the knowledge of incoming war, the Europeans are more concerned about the increase in certain resources and the diminishment of some. In part, some resources can be scarce, which will allow the producer to make gains that will tilt the balance of power. That is all the more reason an enormous amount of time is devoted to the planning and execution of the war in the world. Thus there are wartime and peacetime. Each is legitimately respected in the world of European. War is like a psychedelic drug that the barbarians use to treat their existential anxiety. It is used in therapy just as opium kills pain in some patients in psychiatric hospitals.

7.4. Neurobiology and Language Development

Many people think less of the part that language plays in human intelligence acquisition. In our work, it has been stressed how the Europeans' use of their local languages and, in the addition of scientific methods and theories, gained the upper hand in world affairs. It would be vital to narrate what scientists have discovered recently concerning the source of language as this would help to argue more about how language has helped the Europeans in their knowledge acquisition and, the obtaining of its advantages in learning.

The process of discovering which parts of the brain are involved in language commenced around 1861. It began when a neurosurgeon by the name of Paul Broca of French origin investigated the brain of a dead patient who had had a bizarre disorder. This patient could neither utter a complete sentence nor express his thoughts in writing, though he had been able to comprehend spoken language and did not have any motor impairments of the mouth

or tongue that might have affected his ability to speak. But he could make a sound of the syllable "tan," which came to be used as his name.

As Broca autopsied Tan's brain, he discovered a sizable lesion in the left inferior frontal cortex. Broca then examined eight other patients, all of whom had similar language deficits along with lesions in their left frontal hemisphere. He concluded later that human beings "speak with the left hemisphere" and to identify, for the first time, the existence of a "language center" in the posterior portion of the frontal lobe of this hemisphere. Broca's area became the first area of the brain to be connected with a specific function such as language [29].

Carl Wernicke was a German neurologist who discovered another part of the brain that was involved in understanding language. This lies in the posterior portion of the left temporal lobe. Individuals who had experienced a lesion at this location could speak, but their speech was often incoherent and made no sense.

Wernicke's observations have received confirmation many times from other researchers. Neuroscientists concur that running around the lateral sulcus (also called the fissure of Sylvius) in the left hemisphere of the brain, there is a sort of neural loop that is involved both in comprehension and in producing spoken language. At the frontal end of this loop lies Broca's area, which is usually associated with the production of language or language outputs. At the other end (specifically, in the superior posterior temporal lobe) lies Wernicke's area, which is associated with word processing that we hear being spoken, or language inputs. Broca's area and Wernicke's area are connected by a large bundle of nerve fibers called the arcuate fasciculus [30].

This language loop is in the left hemisphere in about 90% of right-handed persons and 70% of left-handed persons, language being one of the functions that are performed asymmetrically in the brain. Surprisingly, this loop is also found at the same location in deaf persons who use sign language. This loop would not appear to be specific to heard or spoken language, but rather to be more broadly associated with whatever the individual's primary language modality appear to be. Some studies have also suggested a third area to Broca's and Wernicke's areas, this is located in the parietal cortex.

7.5. Models of Spoken and Written Language Functions in the Brain

American neurologist Norman Geschwind in the 1960s and 1970s came out with the first model of the general organization of language functions in the brain. This "associations" model was built on the lesion studies conducted by Wernicke and his successors and is now known as the Geschwind-Wernicke model. In this model, the various characteristics of the language (perception, comprehension, production, etc.) are managed by a distinct functional module in the brain, and each of these modules is linked to the others by a very specific set of serial connections. The central hypothesis of this model is that language disorders arise from breakdowns in this network of connections between these modules.

According to this model, when you hear a word spoken, this auditory signal is processed first in your brain's primary auditory cortex, which then sends it on to the neighboring Wernicke's area. Wernicke's area associates the structure of this signal with the representation of a word stored in your memory, thus enabling you to retrieve the meaning of the particular word. In contrast, when you read a word out loud, the information is perceived first by your visual cortex, which then transfers it to the angular gyrus, from which it is sent to Wernicke's area [31].

The discoveries made by researchers Paul Broca and Carl Wernicke show that language speaking and writing are complex phenomena that must be taken seriously. No wonder it gave the Europeans unique problems when in the beginning they had to depend on Latin to imbibe knowledge and use it to carry out responsibilities. These same problems face the diverse cultures in Africa and other mainstream cultures today in North and South America. Complexities become less when the original languages are being used, it also makes human beings acquire certain characteristics which are possible the many years these languages are being employed by their forebears. These characteristics may be inherited. This knowledge advised many nations to revert to their local languages or use the dominant language among them to communicate. That is one of the reasons I think Europeans are capable of performing well in examinations than many African countries. There will be marginal differences in intelligence

as soon as this problem is removed by the various governments like it has been done in the Far East, especially China and Japan. The deficiencies connected with language are many such that there must be an attempt to cater to them like it is being done in many Western countries. Speech Disorders include Childhood Apraxia of Speech, Dysarthria, Orofacial Myofunctional Disorders, Speech Sound Disorders, Stuttering, Voice Disorders, Aphasia, Selective Mutism, and Childhood Speech Delays. A child who is significantly delayed in developing their language and speech skills might have a language disorder.

Figure 1: Broca's area of the Brain (adapted from Encyclopedia Britannica Online; Retrieved 2023-04-20)

8. Discussion and Concluding Remarks

Neurobiology is a scientific discipline in which researchers investigate the nervous system and how the brain functions. It embraces neuroscience and physiology. Here we encounter the central and peripheral nervous systems of the human organism. These consist of the brain, retina, and spinal cord which form the central nervous system. The peripheral nervous system, on the other hand, encompasses the nerves outside the central nervous system that connect it to the rest of the human body.

In its operations, basic neurobiology at the tissue level is made up of neurons, glial cells, and the extracellular matrix. Neurons are the nervous system's cells that manage information, while the glial cells provide nourishment, protection, and structural support to neurons. The extracellular matrix in the brain gives support on the molecular level for both neurons and glial cells. A specialized type of glial cell which is called the astrocyte still attracts considerable research interest. These cells and the extracellular matrix comprise nerves and the brain regions.

We know that Neurobiology and Cognitive Psychology affect how human beings behave. For example, concerning the former, it is understood that each region of the brain affects a different area of behavior, and neurobiology aims to comprehend these behaviors and their relationship to diverse brain segments. Scientists have, therefore, identified the function of the frontal lobe in contributing to personality, emotions, judgment, problem-solving, abstract thought, attention, and planning. A cardinal distinct role found in the frontal lobe is speech, which is situated in Broca's section. The parietal lobe and the occipital lobe deal with how the human performs interpretation. The parietal lobe contributes to the interpretation of language, visual signals, and spatial perception, while the occipital lobe hosts our visual cortices. The temporal lobe, which harbors the famous Wernicke's section, is a major section of the brain that aids in language understanding. Again, the temporal lobe hosts our auditory cortex and is a significant organ for hearing.

Neurotransmitters function as the body's chemical messengers. These substances convey messages from one nerve cell across a space to the next nerve. They perform one of three functions: exciting, inhibiting, or modulating neurons. Most neurobiological disorders are due to fluctuations in these levels of chemical substances. These

disorders can also be caused by issues in the ways that neurotransmitters are sent or received. Fluctuations can be caused by the over or under-production of neurotransmitters. They can also be caused by damage to the neurons themselves [32, 33 & 34].

Language, therefore, seems to be the work of neurons and in this study, it is found that the use of the blood language or local language played an important function to help the Europeans to carry out functions that led to their enormous success in science. In the first place, it made it easy to organize things through apex comprehension. This provided the ability to discern and enjoyed being mistake-free in a world filled with complex tasks. Citizens became sharpness which was devoid of naivety in dealing with problems. It enhanced creativity that led to writing textbooks and fiction for the entire population. There was originality in accomplishing things which enabled many talented individuals to come out with something new/discoveries. Among the French, English, and later modern Germans, talented people worked with many inventions. In Germany, printing took precedence immediately after citizens decided to give up the French language and depended on their local Dutch language.

Science was the precursor that pushed the Europeans ahead of many nations. Its foundation was laid by the Greeks, the Romans, and the Arabs but it was the Europeans who worked on the principles and popularized them. The discipline consists of rudimentary Science laws, Science theories, Logic, Mathematics, Philosophy, and Ethics. These different disciplines with the local language made it easy to elevate the brain to a new higher level. Neurobiology helped us to stress that constant training aids the brain to make indescribable connections and relationships between events. Logic helped to generate the superior mind which was to reject religious propositions and replace them with objective truth that had been proved by Science.

In scientific terms, the deductive method presents a true statement that is termed a premise. From this general truth, the deductions are made to generate specific knowledge which is of superior quality. Where the premise is false, deductions lose their importance and become worthless which cannot be used for anything. To some extent, false claims will follow.

From a Cognitive psychology perspective, manipulation becomes the source of unstable characteristics that lead to the utilization of guns, intimidation, threats, discrimination, and all other vices.

The hypotheses we have assembled in this article have been observed meticulously by the researcher including the neurobiology ones. In this work, I followed the footsteps of the renowned Physicist, James Clark Maxwell, in his experiment where he observed a little spark along the line that he named the letter ('c') when he was studying electricity and magnetism. This later became known as the speed of light. Albert Einstein was interested in examining how atoms behave in different circumstances such as liquid, which made him put pollen in water molecules. In the microscope, he observed how pollen atoms jingle side by side with water atoms allowing him to coin the term 'Brownian motion.' These experiments were recognized as entailing superb use of the method of observation which was highly emulated by later renowned research scientists around the world.

In the same vein, strict 40 years of observation are almost equal to the microscope and with the readings and research about genetics, I can present the results, which say that the question about "superiority" and "super race" has something to do with the Handicap theory. The theory of handicap, driven by an attempt to cover up some weakness results in the "superiority complex." This has led men to push aside essential truth and instead propagate the opposite, which is associated with superiority. There is a common postulate which says that "*if something deviates from the normal, there is always something abnormal that is enshrined with it.*" The handicap theory has this conventional postulate as its premise.

8.1. Scientific Persuasion and Implication

This article has psychological implications. It is psychological research, and though it is scientific, one needs to utilize interpretation and meaning-making to bring out scientific implications for the study. The world must be careful not to make ideal everything that is suggested by Europeans. Whether it is morality, ethics, behavior principles, manners, conduct, or fabricated world perspectives which go contrary to a particular nation's approach.

Everything that is European should not be made a yardstick because of the lurking manipulation that is always enshrined in their overall behaviors and performances.

Intelligence has something to do with the use of the blood language, local language, or culturally provided language in imbibing knowledge in the physical world. This should be coupled with the use of scientific theories, and appropriate scientific methods which should be driven by the use of Mathematics and logic. The new emerging powerfully technologically economic societies such as China, Malaysia, Singapore, etc., testify to these modern methods of reaching progress in countries.

Declarations

Ethics Declarations

Ethics approval and consent to participate. Regent University Ethics Committee on Research permitted me. Therefore, I acquired the right permission. Furthermore, I tried to hide the identities of the individuals involved in the research.

Informed Consent and Anonymity complied.

Consent for Publication

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Competing interests

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